

ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS for LOADING of NATURAL PLANT EXTRACTS : GREEN NANOTECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT: The effectiveness of naturally occurring plant metabolites utilized for human consumption in cell culture and preclinical animal model systems has been the subject of numerous sorts of research. Significant progress has been achieved in the last few years in creating innovative drug delivery methods that can encapsulate active compounds found in plants, such as organic, inorganic, and hybrid nanoparticles. The process of developing nanoparticles, known as green synthesis, commonly involves the incorporation of plant extracts, cultures of bacteria and fungi, algae, and various other bio-based materials. Compared to microbial synthesis, the use of plant-based green synthesis offers numerous benefits such as simplicity, speed, reliability, affordability, environmental friendliness and a straightforward procedure. The classification, preparation process, and uses of nanoparticles are highlighted in this critical review paper. The invention of innovative nano-carriers for plant active chemicals, their fabrication process, the kind of active components they contain, and their biomedical applications are highlighted in the current review.

KEYWORDS: *Natural plant metabolites, green synthesis, plant extract, carrier formulation, drug delivery, biomedical application, antimicrobial application.*

INTRODUCTION: According to research that was just released, over 70% of newly developed medications have low water solubility, which limits the drug's ability to be absorbed after oral administration [1]. A few of the factors that contribute to the failure of clinical trials are the ingredient's poor solubility, the product's poor stability due to gastric and colonic acidity, the gut microflora's influence on metabolism, the product's poor absorption across the intestinal wall, its poor active efflux mechanism, and the first-pass metabolic effects [2][3]. The controlled release and even efficacy of the bioactivities were improved by the use of novel drug delivery techniques, such as use of nanocarrier delivery, to get beyond the physicochemical and pharmacokinetic limitations of phytochemicals. This breakthrough demonstrates the bright future of nanomedicine as a possible treatment for a wide range of chronic illnesses. Since nanoparticles and nanomaterials have entirely new or improved capabilities based on size, distribution, and morphology, their novel applications are expanding quickly on many fronts.

Numerous fields, including biomedical, health care, food and feed, drug-gene delivery, mechanics, optics, chemical industries, electronics, space industries, energy science, catalysis, light emitters, single electron transistors, nonlinear optical devices, and photo-electrochemical applications, are rapidly embracing its renovation. Significant advancements in these developing technologies have created new foundations and applied frontiers. This involves the subsequent synthesis of nanoscale materials for the purpose of exploring or making use of their enigmatic optoelectronic and physicochemical characteristics [4-6]. Researchers are interested in the metallic nanoparticles because of their remarkable antibacterial properties, which are attributed to their large surface area to volume ratio. These properties are important because of the growing microbial resistance against metal ions, antibiotics, and the emergence of resistant strains. These nanoparticles are used for all the objectives mentioned above [5]. Recently, nanomedicine has gained more attention due to its effectiveness in diagnosing and treating a wide range of illnesses [7]. Thus, the purpose of this review is to illustrate the different kinds of naturally occurring plant products that are loaded with nanocarriers and to highlight their potential application in nanomedicine for a range of illness treatments. A novel drug delivery system (NDDS) is a fresh strategy for distributing pharmaceutical chemicals in the body as needed to safely provide the intended pharmacological effects. It involves creative creation, formulations, new technology, and novel approaches.

CHARACTERISTICS OF NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS:

1. Increases bioavailability.
2. Offer regulated medication administration.
3. Deliver the medication whole to the intended target while avoiding healthy tissue.
4. Delivery remains stable and consistent across a range of physiological factors.
5. Simple to use, trustworthy, and safe.
6. Cost effective.

NANOTECHNOLOGY AND NANOPARTICLES: The term "nanotechnology" describes a young scientific discipline that deals with the creation and synthesis of several types of nanomaterials. Objects with sizes between one and one hundred nm that may differ from the bulk material due to their size are known as nanoparticles. Currently, copper, zinc, titanium, magnesium, gold, alginate, and silver are used to make various metallic applications, including medicinal treatments, the production of solar and oxide fuel batteries for energy storage, and their widespread integration into common products like clothing and cosmetics [8].

A matter particle measuring one to one hundred nanometers is commonly referred to as a nanoparticle. Drug delivery systems that are nanoparticulate have been characterized by a variety of terminology. The medicine is typically delivered using a polymer or lipid carrier, with a particle dimension distribution ranging from a few nanometers to a few hundred nanometers. To support nanoparticles that claim to be drug transporters, novel and inventive polymers have been tried [9].

ADVANTAGES OF NANOPARTICLES:

1. Sustained drug delivery.
2. Protection from degradation.
3. Enhancement of permeability.
4. Decreased side effects compared to conventional drug delivery.
5. Improved therapeutic effect.
6. Nanoparticles can be used to create stronger and more durable materials, improve electrical conductivity, and enhance catalytic activity.
7. In the medical field, nanoparticles can be used for targeted drug delivery, which is a significant advantage.
8. Nanoparticles also have unique magnetic/optical properties, electronic states, and catalytic reactivity that differ from equivalent bulk materials.
9. Nanotechnology has been hailed as the next scientific revolution, with promises of faster computers, cancer treatments.

SYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES USING PLANT EXTRACTS:

Plant extracts have a key role in the nanoparticles production. This method is also known as "green synthesis" or "green nanoparticle manufacturing." *Pelargonium graveolens*, the herb used to make geranium, is utilized to make gold nanoparticles. To create **silver nanoparticles**, mix 5 milliliters of plant extract with 1 milliliter of an aqueous solution of silver nitrate containing 1 millimole. The process for synthesis from alcoholic extract is the same: the plant extract and silver nitrate are stored in a shaker in the dark at 150 rpm [11][12] (In fig 1).

Fig. 1 Synthesis using plant extract

Synthesis of gold nanoparticles: *Pistacia chinensis* Bunge seeds were obtained. Seeds were dried in the shade for 20 days and washed with water to remove the dust. After that, the dried seed was subjected to the grinder to obtain a powder. The powder plant material (1 kg) was soaked in methanol for 10 days to obtain a maximum number of polar secondary metabolites. The extract obtained was concentrated at low temperature and pressure with the help of a rotary evaporator, which afforded 18.9 g extract. To synthesize gold nanoparticles, 2 mg of extract was transferred to 100 mL distilled water and dissolved to prepare stock solution of extract. Similarly, 1 mM stock solution of gold salt (HAuCl_4) was prepared for synthesizing nanoparticles of *Pistacia chinensis* seed extract. To reduce Au^{+3} into Au^0 , the extract solution was combined with a syringe to the salt solution in various ratios. The gold salt solution (HAuCl_4) was kept constant, and the extract concentration was changed (1:1; 1:2; 1:3; 1:4; 1:6; 1:8; 1:10; 1:12, etc.) and then stirred for 30 minutes at 40°C . Then, the solution was kept for stirring continuously for a period of 5 hours to optimize condition for formation of nanoparticles. The change in color indicates the formation of gold nanoparticles.

Synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles: The fresh seeds of *Lathyrus sativus* were collected. The collected seeds were washed thoroughly and immersed in deionized water for 48 h. When the seeds got swelled, the peels were separated from the seeds. After that, the peels were dried at room temperature (48 h, 30–35 °C) and crushed into a fine powdered form using a mortar. About 5 g of peel powder was taken in a round bottom flask containing 100 mL of deionized water and boiled at 70 °C for 60 min. Then the extract was cooled down and filtered using Whatmann filter paper (No. 42). Finally, the resultant peel extract was stored at 4 °C until further use. A 1:2 M ratio of Ferrous Sulphate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and Ferric Chloride ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was dissolved in 50 mL of deionized water and the solution mixture was heated at 80 °C. About 10 mL of *Lathyrus sativus* peel extract was added and the mixture was stirred thoroughly for 5 min. Then, 1 M freshly prepared Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) was gradually added until the pH became 11. After 30 min of continuous stirring, a black-colored product was obtained, which was allowed to cool at room temperature. After that, the precipitate was separated using a ring magnet and washed several times with deionized water to avoid impurities. Finally, the obtained product (Fe_3O_4 -NPs) was subjected to oven-dry at 90 °C for 12 h.

NANOCARRIERS:

The potential application of nanocarriers holds the promise of mitigating the challenges and problems associated with traditional drug delivery methods, including their no specificity, side effects, burst release, and deleterious impact on vast populations of normal cells. Drugs are more bioavailable and therapeutically effective when they are delivered via nanocarrier, which also allows for preferential accumulation at the target site [10]. Many nanocarriers have been created in the modern era, but only a small number of them—particularly anticancer agents—have been clinically approved for the transport of materials. This is due to their motivated actions at the targeted areas.

TYPES OF NANOCARRIERS:

1. ORGANIC NANOCARRIER:

a) Lipid and polymer-based nanocarrier

Lipids facilitate the solubilization of pharmaceuticals in the stomach environment, which lowers their first-pass metabolism by the drug's diffusion through a lymphatic system to the circulatory system. This makes lipids an effective drug penetration enhancer in the digestive tract. The early 1990's saw the development of solid lipid nanoparticle (SLN), a colloidal drug carrier with particle sizes ranging from 50 to 1000 nm (Fig. 2a). Emulsifiers (or combination of them) are used in solid lipid nanoparticle (SLN) processing to stabilize the melted solid lipid(s) in water dispersion. The two most popular techniques for making solid lipid nanoparticle (SLN) are micro emulsification and the high-pressure homogenization (HPH) approach.

Fig.2a Solid Lipid Nanoparticle (SLN)

2b Nanostructured Lipid Carrier (NLC)

The primary benefits of SLN include the provision of a highly lipophilic lipid matrix in which pharmaceuticals can be dispersed, the ability to encapsulate and embed a variety of molecules (including drugs, proteins, antigens, and nucleotides) and the promotion of therapeutic loading into particular tissues and cells. Reducing side effects and enhancing stability both in vivo and invitro are further desirable aspects of SLN. The main difference between SLN and nanoemulsions is that while nanoemulsions solely use liquid lipids, SLN contains both liquid and solid lipids (oils) in its formulation. The most commonly used solid lipid nanoparticle (SLN) is rat puerarin-loaded SLN,

which is distinguished by its quick absorption, somewhat better bioavailability, and higher tissue concentrations in the intended organs (heart and brain). As an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory product, another group created triptolide-loaded solid lipid nanoparticle(SLN), which demonstrated a notable decrease in the activities of myeloperoxidase (MPO) and glutathione (GSH). By reducing direct contact with the mucosal surface, releasing the drug gradually, and avoiding high local drug concentrations, this work aimed to increase solubility, minimize toxicity, hyperemia and irritation to the gastrointestinal tract(GIT)[13]. Better stability, increased drug-loading capacity, reduced drug ejection during depository, and improved drug release control makenanostructured lipidcarrier(NLC) the preferred option over solid lipid nanoparticle(SLN). Therefore, studies aiming at altering water solubility, improving gastrointestinal absorption and oral bioavailability, regulating release, prolonging circulation time by reducing identification by the reticuloendothelial(RES), co-delivery have incorporated a variety of active ingredients into nanostructured lipid carrier(NLC)[14].As a result, it is discovered that nanostructured lipid carriers(NLC) are a superior carrier for the oral administration of a number of chemically and naturally produced substances. Nanostructured lipid carriers(NLC) loaded with cardamom essential oil(CEO) have been effectively created utilizing food-grade lipids, such as olive oil and cocoa butter. 90% of the cardamom essential oil(CEO) loaded nanostructured lipid carriers were small in size, had a loading capacity greater than 25%, and offered strong chemical and physical stability. The inability to apply the cardamom essential oil (CEO) to foods with an aqueous base was overcome by this effort. As a carrier for anticancer properties like zerumbone, thymoquinone, and citral, as well as worthy medication with noticeably enhanced antitumor activity in leukemia and breast tumor cells in vitro and in vivo, a variety of novel and inventive nanostructured lipid carriers are currently being produced.

The spleen, liver, and kidneys contain a high concentration of oil droplets that are engulfed by macrophages after lipophilic drugs are loaded into an oil/water/oil suspension. This is because the amount of liquefied medication absorbed is excessive. The hydrophilic drug is encapsulated in a water/oil or water/oil/waternano emulsion(Fig.4); however, because of its higher internal membrane permeability, it can be well condensed in the lymphatic system through subcutaneous or intramuscular insertion.Targeted sustained release, solubilized component's stability, improved material permeability to mucous membranes and the skin, solubilized components with varying lipophilicity, better drug absorption, reduced viscosity that causes fewer allergic reactions or pain, ease of production and decontamination are some of the system's distinguishing features. Furthermore, the intestinal absorption of nano emulsionsis linked to the lymphatic transport mechanisms that enhance the oral bioavailability of particles in capsules.**Nanosphere:**A colloidal aqueous solution, known as nanosphere, is amorphous or crystalline, and ranges in size from 10 to 200 nm (Fig.3). It is made up of polymeric core that encapsulates the active ingredients and/or absorbs them onto the nanoparticles. Delay in drug release, consistent plasma drug concentrations, increased stability in biologicals fluids, strong defense against chemical and enzymatic degradation, enhanced bioavailability, possible antitumor efficacy, improved total entrapment of the drug, and decreased toxicity are the primary advantages of this system[15]. The hydrophobic surfaces of these particles, which are very sensitive to opsonization and clearance by the reticuloendothelial system, are directly responsible for these most notable characteristics of nanospheres.

Fig. 3 Nanosphere

Fig.4 Nano emulsion

Nanocapsule:Figure 5 illustrates a nano vesicular colloidal dispersion system with a typical core-shell structure, wherein the drug is contained within a cavity or reservoir that is encircled by a polymer membrane or coating. The active ingredient in the cavity may be present as a liquid (an oily or aqueous core), a solid, or a molecular form. The primary characteristics of nano capsule are the core-shell composition and structure, which particularly control drug release. Similar to other formulas, this one can be hydrophobic or lipophilic depending on the raw ingredients and preparation technique. The primary goal in creating this mixture is to change the hydrophilic active ingredient's oral bioavailability.

Fig.5 Nanocapsule

Liposomes:A liposome is a polar lipid nanoparticle with a spherical shape. It is made up of one or more natural or synthetic lipid bilayer membranes that enclose an aqueous core into which the aqueous core freely diffuses(Fig.6a). It is well known that a liposome can load both hydrophilic and lipophilic materials and have one or more homocentric membranes due to the presence of both hydrophilic and lipophilic groups on the same molecule.By encapsulating medications, vitamins, herbs, and enzymes with liposomes, the pharmacokinetic profiles of these substances can be greatly altered for the production of vaccines, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals. The ability of liposomes to accommodate both lipid-and water-soluble agents and form phospholipid bilayers gives them the unique ability to improve a product's solubility, bioavailability, delivery, intracellular uptake, and biodistribution performance in both in vitro and in vivo settings. Furthermore, their use in biomedicine formulations has increased due to their ability to protect active drug from environmental factors, their powerful primal destruction of the loaded material, and their quick, low-costtreatment with minimal systemic morbidity [16].**Transferosomes** are made up of phospholipids and a single chain surfactant, which give the vesicles their elasticity and deformability(Fig.6b). These vesicles can be applied topically on the skin with nutrients locally. This special infrastructure makes it possible to transfer drugs that are hydrophilic, lipophilic, or amphiphilic. As a result, it can be used to carry drugs that have a wide range of solubility and be used as drug carriers for small molecules, peptides, proteins, and herbal components [7]. However, due to their susceptibility to oxidative degradation, transferosomes lack chemical stability. Moreover, the natural phospholipid's purity poses a challenge to the use of transferosomes as drug delivery systems.

Fig.6A Schematic Illustration of (a)Liposome, (b)Transfersome, (c)Niosome, (d)Ethosome.

Niosome: A niosome is a nonionic nanosphere vesicle that has a diameter ranging from 100 nm to 2 μ m. Its lamellar phase is composed of layers of nonionic amphiphilic lipids that encircle its watery center (Fig.6c). It is made using the following techniques: proniosome pre-formulation, sonication, micro fluidization, multiple membrane extrusion, reverse phase evaporation, remote loading, bubble method, and thin-film hydration. Niosomes and liposomes share a similar structure, but niosomes may be more advantageous than liposomes due to their greater penetration ability, greater stability, higher therapeutic index of a drug, and lower toxicity [17]. Niosome has several benefits, such as controlled content release, high solubility, and flexibility. It is also reasonably priced. As a result, they have been extensively used as a neoplasia targeting vehicle as well as peptide, hemoglobin, and transdermal delivery.

The phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylserine, phosphatidylethanolamine, and phosphatidylglycerol are among the phospholipids that make up an ether, along with water and a relatively high (30-45%) alcohol concentration made up of ethanol and isopropyl alcohol [18][19]. Because of the flexibility of the lecithin bilayer, this composition, as opposed to liposomes, prolongs the physical stability of ethosomes and improves topical drug delivery of highly concentrated active ingredients and transdermal transport efficiency[18]. The drawback of ethosome is that it grows in size from tens of nanometers to micrometers because of its poor stability, which is brought on by alcohol evaporating and eventually leaking loaded compounds. Alcohol can be combined with trehalose and propylene glycol to mitigate this drawback[14].

Phytosome: Phytosome is a proprietary formula designed to add water-soluble phytochemicals and active ingredients from medicinal plants to phospholipids to form lipid-compatible molecular complexes that can significantly alter absorption and bioavailability[20]. The unique feature of phytosome formulation is that, depending on the substance(s) conjugated, phosphatidylcholine and the plant materials form a molecular complex and chemical bonding at a ratio of either 1:1 or 2:1. In contrast, no chemical bonds form in liposomes, and thousands of phosphatidylcholine molecules enclosing the water-soluble compound are freely visible. A Phyto lipid delivery system is a specially designed phytosome that is used to deliver herbal medications. It is created by combining water-soluble phytochemicals or standardized plant extracts with phospholipids to create lipid-compatible complexes that improve absorption and bioavailability without requiring pharmacological or structural alterations to the constituent parts.

The enterocyte cell membrane is made up of small particles called phytosomes (Fig. 7), which have the ability to better transit from a water-soluble state to a lipid-soluble state before entering the cell and ultimately reaching the bloodstream. This process shields the valuable components of the herbal medication from the destruction of gastric enzymes and gut bacteria.

Fig.7: Phytosome

b) Biopolymer-Based Nanocarrier (BBN): They have been derived from polysaccharides (chitosan, hyaluronan, dextran, cyclodextrins, pectin, guar gum, cellulose, sodium alginate, and starch) and/or proteins (gelatin, albumin, and milk proteins), and/or their modified forms, derivatives, or combinations. These materials have several intriguing properties that make them suitable for the production of biopolymer-based nanocarrier, including biological realization, bioactivity, biodegradability, low toxicity, ease of modification, and ease of gel production. Because of their varied charges, molecular weights, and compositions, this kind of nanocarrier has been shown to have plausible water solubility, stability, degradation, and biocompatibility for a broad range of applications.

Coacervation, spray drying, electrospinning, electrospray, supercritical fluid, emulsion-diffusion, reverse micelle, emulsion-droplet coalescence, emulsification/solvent evaporation, salting-out, ultrasonication, and high-pressure homogenization are just a few of the techniques for fabricating biopolymer-based nanocarrier delivery systems that are well-addressed. Chitosan is a cationic linear polysaccharide that is biocompatible, biodegradable, and contains d-glucosamine and N-acetyl glucosamine units. It is extracted from the exoskeleton of crustacean arthropods, which include insects, crabs, lobster, and shrimp. It is purported to be the best example of a naturally occurring, pure biopolymer that can deliver plant components, such as trans-resveratrol, curcumin, and quercetin, with improved mucoadhesion, solubility, and dissolution rate. Chitosan has also been used in a number of biomedical applications, including bone healing, tissue engineering scaffolds, drug delivery systems, surgical thread manufacturing, and wound dressings. Well-developed and possessing sophisticated qualities, chitosan can change its surface charge, produce pH-sensitive swelling, increase stability, and boost bioactivity by adjusting its targeting to the precise site of action.

Cross-linked polymeric networks known as hydrogels have hydrophilic functions that provide spaces for the homing of aqueous biological fluids. Hydrogels are considered to be a promising biocompatible material with a wide range of therapeutic applications[14]. Adorable hydrophilicity, high porosity, and controlled drug release are the characteristics of this formula. Inherently biodegradable biopolymer based nanocarrier is constructed from naturally occurring biopolymers, including chitosan, alginate, hyaluronic acid (HA), collagen, and gelatin. These biopolymers are often pre-functionalized to integrin binding sites, enabling adherence and integrated cellular responses [7]. The application of these compounds is limited, though, as there is notable batch-to-batch variability and possible immunogenicity in foreign model organisms.

2. INORGANIC NANOCARRIER:

A variety of nanocarrier types have been created recently and are being researched for their potential to deliver active ingredients found in plants

Metal Nanoparticles (MN):

These nanoparticles which include cerium oxide (CeO₂), iron oxide (Fe₃O₄), yttrium oxide (Y₂O₃), titanium dioxide (TiO₂), silver nanoparticles (AgNP_s), gold nanoparticles (AuNP_s), copper nanoparticles (CuNP_s), zinc oxide (ZnO NP_s) nanoparticles, quantum dots, and cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles, have unique advantages in biomedical applications because they contain essential mineral elements that have strong biological effects. The ability of these nanoparticles to bind drugs through covalent conjugation or noncovalent interaction can be attributed to their structural diversity, low toxicity, and high biocompatibility. They can therefore be used to achieve controlled release and intercellular drug delivery via a photothermal pathway. In an effort to enhance intracellular drug delivery, counteract multi-drug resistant (MDR), accelerate anti-tumor activity, and reduce side effects, a novel metal nanoparticle with multi-functional groups is also being studied through the development of complex metal nanoparticle integrated multifunctional liposomes loaded with active components. In order to accelerate the healing process of wound infections brought on by hyperglycemia, it has recently been demonstrated that biopolymers complexed with bioactive nanoparticles endowing antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties have a fantastic effect on wound care.

Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticle (MSN):

Most recently, Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticle has emerged as a promising drug delivery and storage medium. It features a large surface area with a high therapeutic agent loading capacity, high pore volume and porosity (honeycomb-like architecture), adjustable pore diameter, modifiable surface potential, controllable morphology, charming biocompatibility, and controlled release properties. Additionally, Mesoporous Silica nanoparticle has been used in pharmaceuticals to deliver drugs with cellular targetability, decrease drug toxicity, and increase drug bioavailability. Specifically, the remarkable advancements in the creation of microporous silica nanoparticle-based efficient delivery systems for therapeutic genes, anticancer agents, and poorly soluble medications.

Magnetic Nanoparticle (MNP):

The use of developed magnetic nanoparticles, particularly iron oxide, has been linked to the best trigger drug release, highest target positioning, biocompatibility, and nontoxicity in a magnetic field. Clinical applications of magnetic nanoparticles with suitable surface coatings include drug delivery, tissue repair, magnetic resonance imaging, hyperthermia, cell and tissue targeting, and transfection. Additional advantages of using magnetic nanocarriers include the ability to treat illnesses more quickly and effectively even with small doses of the medication; this can lower the concentration of the medication in healthy tissues and, as a result, lessen side effects.

Calcium Carbonate (CaCO₃) Nanoparticle:

A straightforward automated stirring of cockle shell powder in the presence of BS-12 as a biomineralization catalyst produced an aragonite CaCO₃ nanoparticle that is less stressful to produce, pleasant for the environment, and less expensive. Due to its biocompatibility, nontoxicity, variable surface chemistry, good physicochemical properties, ease of bulk preparation, slow biodegradability, pH sensitivity, and porous nature, CaCO₃ is used as therapeutic agent with exceptional efficacy.

APPLICATIONS OF NANOPARTICLES:

1. Cosmetics and Sunscreens:

Long-term stability during use is absent from conventional UV protection sunscreens. The sunscreen that contains nanoparticles, like titanium dioxide, has many benefits. Because titanium oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles are

transparent to visible light, they offer UV protection. Some sunscreens have light as well as the ability to absorb and reflect UV rays. A few iron oxide nanoparticles are used as a pigment in cosmetics such as lipsticks.

2. Medicine:

The application of nanoparticles in drug delivery has advanced the field of medicine to thanks to nanotechnology. Nanoparticles can be used to deliver the medication to particular cells. By administering the medication in the prescribed dosage and location, overall amount of drug consumed and its side effects are greatly reduced. This process lowers the price and adverse consequences. Tissue engineering, which replicates and repairs damaged tissue, conducted with the assistance of nanotechnology.

3. Electronics:

The increased demand for large-sized, high-brightness displays in televisions and computer monitors these days is driving the use of nanoparticles in display technology. For instance, zinc selenide and sulphide, cadmium sulphide, and nanocrystalline lead telluride are used in contemporary display light emitting diodes (LED). The rise in popularity of portable consumer electronics like laptops and cell phones created a huge need for small, light, and high-capacity batteries. The best option for battery separator plates is nanoparticles. Significantly more energy can be stored than conventional batteries because of the foam-like structure of their aerogel. Nanocrystalline batteries, because of their large surface area, metal hydrides and nickel require less charging and last longer. Gases like NO₂ and NH₃ are detected using nanoparticle's increased electrical conductivity. This is because the gas molecules bind the nanoparticles together, increasing their pores and facilitating charge transfer from the nanoparticles to NO₂. This makes the nanoparticles more effective gas sensors.

4. Catalysis:

Higher catalytic activity is provided by the high surface area of nanoparticles. The incredibly high surface to volume ratio of these nanoparticles makes them effective an effective catalyst for the synthesis of chemicals. The use of platinum nanoparticles in the automotive industry is one of the significant applications. Catalytic converters, because of their extremely large surface area, which lowers the amount of platinum needed for the nanoparticles, considerably lowering the price and enhancing performance. A certain chemical for instance, nanoparticles are used in the reduction of nickel oxide to nickel metal(Ni).

5. Food:

By using nanotechnology, food production, processing, preservation, and packaging are all improved. For instance, in the food packaging process, a nanocomposite coating can introduce anti-microbial agents directly on to the coated film surface.

3. BIOLOGICAL NANOCARRIERS: These are extremely varied, naturally occurring nanoparticles that have a shell made of capsid proteins around the DNA or RNA viral genome. They range in size (in the nanometer range) and morphology from icosahedrons to simple spheres to rods. Viruses are specifically designed to target the most noticeable organisms and tissues in this regard. The majority of applications use native viral capsid proteins without nucleic acid as virus nanoparticles (VNP) and virus-like particles (VLP) acid to prevent the spread of infection [21]. The self-assembling, durable protein nets known as VVNP and VLP are nanosized (about 100 nm), with distinct shape and homogenous nanostructures. These days, this technology is employed in many different ways, including spherical or filamentous scaffolds, medication delivery, and gene therapy. NP and VLP are strong protein nets that are self-assembled and nanosized (about 100 nm), with distinct shape and homogenous nanostructures. These days, this system serves a variety of functions, including gene therapy and medication administration nano reactors, spherical or filamentous scaffolds [14].

In vivo vaccinations employing modified VNP and VLP are also used to change other diseases or to create protection against the parent virus. Furthermore, VLP conjugated to suitable epitopes has been employed in anti-tumor as well as for vaccinations against long-term conditions like high blood pressure [22]. In relation to their application in bioimaging systems, VLP has additionally been modified for use as contrast agents in PET and MRI systems. Additionally, VLP's innate propensity for specific cell types enable selective distribution, and the VLP can be altered for cell-specific delivery by conjugating to targeting molecules like folic acid.

CONCLUSION: The medicinal efficacy of naturally occurring potential natural plant products has been hindered by their insufficient solubility in water and absorption. Recent research has attempted to use nanocarriers to overcome these issues, and studies have predicted that nanomedicine will be a practical method for managing, diagnosing, and imaging for a range of illness care and treatment including cancer, diabetes, hyperglycaemia, hypertension, and anaemia. There are various formulations of natural plant extract with nanocarrier encapsulation under clinical or preclinical trial development, and a number of them have already received FDA approval for safe human use, particularly those for which it has been established that they do not pose a risk of long-term toxicity, depletion, and insufficient metabolism after being reduced by the idea of alterations and pilot research, which might be created as a low-cost, safe, feasible, and suitable method for regulating and managing disease.

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